

TEACHING LISTENING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH INTERACTIVE MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The Article are considered teaching listening foreign languages through interactive multimedia technologies. Multimedia technologies mean use of such audiovisual and interactive tutorials as:1) Software (multimedia disks, presentations, audio and video clips. resources of the Internet);2) Hardware (personal computer (PC), audio - video - equipment, multimedia projector, interactive board or smart board).Video courses, being good addition to the lesson maintenance, can introduce sociocultural realias: mimicry and gestures, clothes, surrounding conditions. Besides, on the basis of these video courses, teacher can set various role-play games and organise discussions, debates for the purpose of repetition of the passed lexical material.

Key words: approach, multimedia, interactive, practice, technology, motivation, equipment.

INTRODUCTION

The modern communicatively approach teaching prepares students to use foreign languages in real-life conditions. Use of interactive multimedia technologies in communicative teaching foreign language considerably raises quality of giving material of a lesson and efficiency of mastering of this material by students. As practice

shows, use and introduction of modern technologies, the multimedia equipment enriches the maintenance of educational process, raises motivation of pupils to learn English language and at the same time close cooperation between teacher and students is achieved. Multimedia technologies mean use of such audiovisual and interactive tutorials as:

1) **Software (multimedia disks, presentations, audio and video clips. resources of the Internet);**

2) **Hardware (personal computer (PC), audio - video - equipment, multimedia projector, interactive board or smart board).** Video courses, being good addition to the lesson maintenance, can introduce sociocultural realities: mimicry and gestures, clothes, surrounding conditions. Besides, on the basis of these video courses, teacher can set various role-play games and organise discussions, debates for the purpose of repetition of the passed lexical material. Audiocassettes and disks which are an obligatory component of modern foreign language teaching, contain records of texts and tasks for audition, songs, rhymes, exercises which are an effective method of working on a pronunciation. Records are recorded by professional sound technicians with participation of specially invited actors - of native speakers. Nowadays there is a set of multimedia tutorials, such as interactive courses «Tell me more», «English: a way to perfection», children's encyclopaedias (for example: «Encyclopaedia Britannica»), etc. They are calculated on training speech activities: reading, writing, listening, and speaking; they also contain explanation and repetition of a various grammatical material with corresponding tasks and exercises, as for independent training, and work in a group. If teacher can choose appropriate materials correctly necessary to pupils and use it in the form accessible to pupils, both pupils and teacher will benefit a lot.

DISCUSSION

Teacher can use lesson plans created independently, for example, on PowerPoint presentation. This program is convenient and in performing creative design works by pupils with the subsequent demonstration to a class. Advantages of design work are already known for a long time and are used as a technique of teaching various school subjects, including foreign languages. Students are involved in creative research process, as all projects are the individual-focused kind of work and as they write about themselves, their family, their house, and hobbies. Performance and presentation of projects gives possibility to children with different level of language to act and express their ideas, opinions on a certain theme that promotes development of informative activity, imagination, self-discipline, skills of joint activity. [net. 1]

Much interactive software allows access to the sources located the Internet that helps pupils to understand and acquire a studied material more deeply.

For today the most universal mean of training are electronic interactive boards, for example SMART Board. Electronic interactive board is an effective way of introduction of the electronic maintenance of a teaching material and multimedia materials in teaching process. Thematic texts in English prepared in advance, training and verifying exercises, colourful pictures of various character, a material of English-speaking multimedia disks, audio - video data serve for introduction or activization of a material of a lesson, repetition or fastening of lexical units and grammatical structure of language, the control and self-checking of knowledge.

Interactive board allows to work without use of keyboard, "mouse" and computer monitor. All necessary actions can be made directly on the screen by means of a special marker or even a finger. The teacher does not distract from a lesson for carrying out necessary manipulations behind the computer. It positively affects quality of giving a teaching material together with interactive SMART Board there software called SMART Notebook is delivered. It allows creating records which can include various types of information (texts, videos, schemes, tables, signs and drawings). The Software possesses such possibilities:

1) In explaining a grammatical material (for example: drawing up various types of sentences) helps to allocate use of multi-coloured pencils to highlight main things, to direct attention to the use of the necessary form of a notional verb and a site auxiliary in the offer.

2) It is possible to embody ways of thought on the screen, to fix an operating procedure, and, if necessary, there is a possibility to return to the beginning of a statement or more difficult aspect of a material of a lesson (for example: a theme «the Difference in use and formation of tenses "Simple" and "Progressive").

3) All material of the spent lesson with an interactive board can be kept in record and the teacher does not have necessity to write and create all anew.

Methodologists have long held that images enhance comprehension, storage, and recall of information. Visuals support comprehension and form-meaning correspondence, both of which contribute to higher levels of learner motivation. Including visuals for listening skills development also finds support when rates of spoken language and the human ability to process incoming aural information are considered. We process what we hear much more quickly than the time it takes for the message to be spoken. While we listen, we have time to infer and elaborate.

When students listen to a cassette or to a person speaking they may find it a challenge. This is because they have no visual clues and may think that they will not understand. Also, we usually only have once chance to hear something. This is why;

we need to start by doing activities to prepare students. Then we need to do the activities in which the students need to use the information from the item they have listened to. The main sub-skills of listening are predicting listening for the main idea (skimming), listening for specific information (scanning). When the language is our own first language, there is sufficient time and opportunity to mentally act upon the incoming stream by creating connections, making transformations, interpretations, and mental images. When aural input is in a language for which we have a limited ability, additional effort must be expended:

Visual support provides the learner hooks on which to hang meaning and make sense of the aural stream. While learner response to video as an instructional tool has been positive across disciplines, it has been particularly strong for language teaching. Video can fill in gaps in aural comprehension which at once lowers affect and empowers the language learner. Video is widely considered more powerful, more salient, and more comprehensible than other media for second and foreign language students. In rare empirical studies, video-based instruction is consistently preferred over other language learning activities as well as over audio-only instruction. Multimedia systems with video under learner control are also preferred over other instructional activities. In short, multiplying input modalities to include full motion video apparently motivates learners and engages their attention to aural input. The co-occurrence of video with text, audio, and graphics in the multi-media environment does raise the issue of the amount of processing these combined input modalities entail and whether these cognitive demands limit or lengthen task persistence. Multi-modal materials, then, potentially support comprehension of the message as opposed to drawing attention to its constituent parts. [3].

Video has been proved to be an effective method in teaching English as a foreign/second language (EFL/ESP) for both young and adult learners. Teachers and students can always create their own videotapes as content for the class or as a means to assess learners' performance. Teaching English non-EFL classes by designing lessons and activities that students will implement as individuals or in groups with the aim to develop their language competence and performance and to use English, perhaps, in similar situations to those included in each videotaped segment. Once we implement the videotaped material with the above-mentioned objectives, we will provide students with opportunities to practice using the language skills in authentic communicative setting.

The aim of the article and the activities held by us serve a two-fold purpose: (1) the pedagogic, and (2) the pragmatic. It also incorporates English language teaching with the teaching of cultural values that an EFL learner is likely to encounter once s/he is stationed in an English native speaking environment.

Using video material in a non-English Language Teaching (ELT) environment can motivate students. They will undergo a special experience of real feelings of accomplishment when they understand what is going on in a situation where native speakers use English. Thus, an EFL learner will realize that “with a bit of extra effort and practice, along with some help from the teacher, ‘real English’ is not beyond their comprehension. As we have noticed, video material can be a very useful source and asset for the language teaching-learning process because it combines both fun and pedagogic instructions in an authentic material that reflect real interaction. By employing videotaped material teachers can always create an indefinite number of language teaching activities. It is well known that listening comprehension plays a key role in foreign language teaching, especially with young learners. Web sites for children, if appropriately selected and organized, can offer a range of opportunities to develop foreign language listening and proficiency in a playful and enjoyable context. Tales and stories are effective listening materials for children to develop listening comprehension and literacy both in their first and foreign language. Besides, they present linguistic forms, grammar, phrases, vocabulary, and formulaic speech within a meaningful and structured context that supports comprehension of the narrative world. This verbal information is commonly complemented with non-verbal information in the form of large pictures, which helps children reconstruct the storyline [2:239-258]

CONCLUSION

Multimedia applications for foreign language learning can provide a more realistic picture of the new language and culture in the classroom, including not only linguistic but also paralinguistic features such as body language, gestures, prosody, etc., which help to convey meaning to the learners. It is believed in this study that digital stories, if appropriately elected, can prove to be very useful in developing children's listening skills. They tend to be visual, interactive and reiterative. Usually, learners have to listen to and understand a simple order in order to proceed with the story by clicking on parts of the screen or the picture. The interactivity of Internet-based stories, we assume, may facilitate learning since children are actively involved in decoding and understanding the story. [1:35-56] In spite of all these potential benefits, however, there is insufficient research on how Internet-based technology contributes to improve children's linguistic comprehension. Only a few studies suggest that the use of computer-based technologies in the classroom is correlated to positive academic outcomes, including higher test scores [4]. Many English language teachers might be attracted by the resources the Internet can bring into the classroom but are often overwhelmed by a large quantity of sites and materials that often exceed the linguistic level and the technological abilities of their students. Real adaptation of these resource

books into the classroom, we believe, has not taken place yet. Many professionals feel uncertain on how to take advantage of the Web to bring that part of the world into the language classroom, especially when working with young learners.

All of this suggests the need of conducting further research on the use of Internet-based content and methodology in language learning settings. Only with sufficient objective data and results will we be able to assess the effects that computer-mediated instruction actually exerts on language acquisition processes.

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